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Comparison of the Efficacy of Three Treatment Methods for Advanced Osteoarthritis of the Knee

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ABSTRACT

Objective: To compare, analyze and evaluate the clinical efficacy of the combination of Total knee arthroplasty (TKA) only, TKA with anti-osteoporosis medicine, and KOA with anti-osteoporosis for the patients with severe osteoarthritis and osteoporosis.

Methods: A retrospective study was conducted Between September 2019 and April 2021; 90 patients with advanced Osteoarthritis or rheumatoid arthritis 60 of them underwent total knee arthroplasty. The total patients were divided into three groups based on the treatment options: 30 patients underwent total knee arthroplasty (TKA)only, and another 30 patients had undergone total knee arthroplasty (TKA) with anti-osteoporosis medicine (calcium, VitD3, Elcatonin, Diacerein) for treatment. In contrast, the last 30 patients with KOA treat only with anti-osteoporosis medicine. The clinical efficacy parameters of the three groups (age, sex, hospital duration, BMI, Serum β -ctx, Serum vitamin D3, Serum N-mid, HSS score, Vas score) were compared using Spss 26.0 statistical software for statistical analysis. The measured data were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation ($\bar{x} \pm s$). Categorical data were tested by chi-square test, data obeying normal distribution by t-test, and data not obeying normal distribution by rank-sum test. The p-value for the test level was $P < 0.05$ the differences were statistically significant.

Results: Mean age of patient were 65.13 ± 6.47 in the Total knee arthroplasty (TKA) only group and 67.73 ± 8.01 years in the Total knee arthroplasty (TKA) with anti-osteoporosis

medicine group, 67.5 ± 6.64 years in KOA with anti-osteoporosis group there was no statistically difference mean age between three groups $P > 0.05$. Patients with Total knee arthroplasty (TKA) with anti-osteoporosis medicine group demonstrate shorter hospital stay duration, higher HSS score, shorter VAS score, while the TKA with anti-osteoporosis and KOA with anti-osteoporosis demonstrate higher serum vitamin D3, lower serum β -ctx, serum N-mid level, BMD, than Total knee arthroplasty (TKA) only group. There was no statistically significant difference regarding BMI $P < 0.05$

Conclusion: The treatment efficacy of the combination of Total knee arthroplasty (TKA) with anti-osteoporosis and KOA with anti-osteoporosis drug than only Total knee arthroplasty (TKA) treatment for end-stage, posttraumatic Osteoarthritis is more advantageous, safest and precise, which is worth being applied in clinical practice.

Keywords

knee osteoarthritis, osteoporosis, total knee arthroplasty, clinical efficacy, anti-osteoporosis treatment.

Introduction

Osteoporosis (OP) and Osteoarthritis (OA) of the knee are a group of highly prevalent diseases in elderly patients and often occur together, seriously affecting patients' quality of life. Because the main risk factors of osteoporosis are aging and low body weight. The main risk factors of knee osteoarthritis (OA) are aging and obesity. These diseases have an inverse relationship. The most common clinical treatment for knee OA is Total knee arthroplasty (TKA), and patients and Clinicians have unanimously recognized its efficacy. However, because most patients with OA of the knee are also affected by OP, which can lead to the destruction of bone mass and bone volume, failure to provide timely and effective treatment may result in joint pain and loosening of the prosthesis after knee replacement due to insufficient bone strength, which may affect the postoperative outcome. It is believed that the decrease in subchondral bone mineral density (BMD) in osteoporotic patients is the initial stage of Osteoarthritis [1]. The prevalence of preoperative osteoporosis in patients awaiting primary TKA is not well investigated. A Few studies have investigated osteoporosis in patients waiting for elective TKA [2-4]. The prevalence of preoperative osteoporosis was reported to be 23-33%. In studies with the Asian population, osteoporosis was 23% and 31%. Therefore, it is important to use anti-osteoporosis drugs to provide effective treatment after surgery and severe KOA in young patients. In this study, we investigated the Effect of anti-osteoporosis medication on the clinical outcome of KOA patients who underwent TKA and severe KOA young patients.

Materials and methods

Between September 2019 to April 2021, 90 patients with severe Osteoarthritis were treated in the traumatology department of the second affiliated hospital of Kunming Medical University. There were 26 males and 64 females. We were divided equally into three groups. The first group of 30 patients was treated with total knee arthroplasty only, and the second group of 30 patients was treated with total knee arthroplasty with anti-osteoporosis medicine. In contrast, in the third group, KOA treated only anti-osteoporosis medicine. All patients gave their informed consent to participate. The patients' clinical efficacy and symptom relief were

investigated by telephone and home visits, and the follow-up period was six months. The Inclusion criteria were patients above 50 years of age, Patients that have severe rheumatoid arthritis or The patient has advanced Osteoarthritis with osteoporosis and Exclusion criteria were patients who have A history of thrombotic disease, cardiopulmonary insufficiency, psychiatric disease, morphine or local anesthetic allergy, Prior injury to the medial or lateral collateral ligaments of the knee. These patients have had knee surgery, Patients with NSAID allergy patients who have joint trauma or metabolic bone diseases. The demographic and clinical data like age, sex, hospital stay, BMI, side replacement, serum β -ctx, serum vitamin D, serum N-mid, BMD, VAS score, HSS score was observed and compared between three groups, total knee arthroplasty only and total knee arthroplasty with anti-osteoporosis medicine and KOA with anti-osteoporosis.

Preparation before surgery:

Initially, after hospitalization, various general relevant examinations were done. Blood Hb%, blood grouping and cross-matching, fasting and postprandial blood sugar, blood urea and serum creatinine, urine albumin, sugar, serum vitamin D, β -ctx, N-mid were sent to the lab. Also checking before Operation the BMI, bone mineral density (BMD) in DEXA scan, Hospital for special surgery (HSS score), visual analog scale (VAS score, Radiographic examination of patients like x-ray taking for three group patients. The respective department evaluated patients for medical problems and treated them accordingly to avoid anesthetic risk. Available prophylactic antibiotics are given before surgery.

During surgery:

After general anesthesia, the patient is placed in the prone position with a disinfected towel (centered on the proposed surgical incision in the affected knee). A sterile tourniquet is placed at the base of the affected thigh. The anterior median incision was made in the affected knee (from approximately 7-8 cm proximal to the patella to approximately the medial tibial tuberosity), and the joint was entered via the internal 1/3 of the quadriceps tendon, bypassing the medial edge of the patella to the tibial tuberosity, removing the subpatellar fat pad, hyperplasia, meniscus, synovial membrane, cruciate ligament depending on the intra-articular situation. The cement was filled, the prosthesis was installed, the pressure was applied until the cement was solid, the excess cement around the joint was removed, a suitable platform prosthesis was selected and installed, the knee was checked in extension and flexion for elasticity and patellar movement, the patella was denervated, a drainage tube was placed, the incision was closed layer by layer, and a compression bandage was applied.

Figure : 1

An osteotomy guides the plate to the distal femur by a fixation screw. The distal thigh osteotomy plate guided the tibial surface guide plate. The distal femoral osteotomy plate is joined to the femoral side, then the osteotomy is added to the distal front of the femur. The distal thigh osteotomy guidance plate was screwed to the distal femur end. Removed the connecting rod to release the distal thigh osteotomy guiding plate. An osteotomy guide plate was connected to the thigh, and the surgery began. Knee flexion, thigh bone size, and force line of the lower extremities, anterior cortex of the femurs were exposed using a typical four-in-one osteotomy plate, and the extension or flexion of the distal anterior condyle's osteotomy line in the sagittal plane was confirmed. The anterior osteotomy surface of the femurs reveals no bending or overextension after osteotomy.

Figure : 2

The proximal tibia was reconstructed using a bone graft after the anterior and posterior femoral condyles were osteotomized. Once the test mold has been satisfied, it should be removed. It was administered posteriorly and subperiosteally around the femur and tibia using a mixture of medications (ropivacaine 300mg, flurbiprofen axetil 50mg, betamethasone 1.0ml, morphine 10mg, epinephrine 0.5mg). After rinsing the joint cavity, place

the cemented prosthesis in the joint. To achieve peripheral denervation, osteophytes surrounding the patella were removed during the drying process of the cement. Once the cement has dried, the joint cavity is rinsed again, and the cocktail mixture (which does not contain the chemical betamethasone) is injected into the joint capsule and subcutaneously. It was decided to use an intraarticular injection of 10 g/L of tranexamic acids to treat the articular cavity. A negative pressure drainage tube was placed, and the incision was closed layer-by-layer. The drain tube was clamped for 2 hours, and the incision was lightly wrapped. While the procedure was performed, a tourniquet was applied, and the incision was sutured and wrapped.

Postoperative management:

All TKA two patients were treated with anti-inflammatory, analgesic, anti-swelling, hydro/electrolytic balance and nutritional support therapies. On the first postoperatively day, the patients performed contraction exercises such as dorsiflexion of the affected limb and leg kicking at the bedside with the lower leg hanging down. On the second postoperative day, after removing the drainage tube, they gradually walked with the assistance of a walker. In the first group and second group, anti-osteoporosis was started; these patients were treated with oral alfacalcidol, calcitriol D plus anti-osteoporosis medicine on the second day, patients came out outpatient clinic for frontal and lateral radiographs, bone mineral density, physical examination at least once every two months after surgery group and group two and also group three.

Outcome measures:

The primary outcomes like duration of hospital stay, bone mineral index (BMI), bone mineral density (BMD) DXA scan, serum B-ctx, serum vitaminD3, and serum N-mid were measured before VAS score, HSS score, measured before and after all three groups.

Statistical analysis:

Statistical methods Spss 26.0 statistical software was used for statistical analysis. The measured data were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation (\pm s). Categorical data were tested by the chi-square test, data that obeyed normal distribution and satisfied chi-square were tested by the F test, and data that did not obey normal distribution were tested by the rank sum test. The p-value of the test level was $0.05 < 0.05$ difference was statistically significant.

Results:

Table 1: The table showing BMD before surgery and after 6 months of treatment

Group	N	BMD before surgery (SD)	6 months after surgery BMD (SD)
TKA	30	-2.1±0.94	-2.1733±1.4579
TKA+anti	30	-2.93±1.24	-1.5167±0.47495
KOA+Anti	30	-2.93±1.24	-1.665±0.59265
F/H值		5.255	16.817
P值		0.007	0.02

The bone mineral density of all three groups was evaluated before a surgery and 6 months later. The first group receiving TKA had a value of -2.1 before surgery and -2.17 after 6 months. The BMD of the second group getting TKA with anti-osteoporosis therapy was -2.9 before operation and -1.5 after 6 months. Only anti-osteoporosis medicines were used in the third group to treat knee osteoarthritis, and the BMD decreased from -2.9 to -1.6. Using ANOVA, the mean F/H was 5.255 before surgery and 16.817 6 months later. The mean P-value was 0.007, showing that the variation in bone mineral density before surgery was statistically significant, $P < 0.05$. At the same time, the difference in the sixth month after surgery was not statistically significant ($P > 0.005$).

Table 2: The table showing N-MID before surgery and after 6 months of treatment

Group	N	Before surgery, N-MID (ng/ml)	6months after surgery N-MID (ng/ml)
TKA	30	16.69±8.11	19.49±8.48
TKA+anti	30	20.6213±7.6132	12.4497±3.39961
KOA+anti	30	20.7547±7.26299	11.583±2.35513
F/H值		2.726	25.075
P值		0.071	0.01

N-MID osteocalcin ELISA test was performed in all three groups. N-MID increased from 16.6 to 19.4 nanograms per milliliter in the first group with just TKA. N-MID was 20.6 before and 12.44 after six months of surgery in the second group with combined therapy. N-MID was 20.75 before and 11.58 after six months in the last group of patients treated with anti-osteoporosis medicines. The N-MID decreased in groups 2 and

3. The ANOVA test was applied, and the mean H/F was 2.726 before surgery and 25.075 in the sixth month after surgery. N-MID difference after surgery was statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). While the difference in pre-surgical N-MID ($P > 0.05$) was not statistically significant.

Table 3: The table showing Vit D before treatment and after 6 months of treatment

Group	N	Vit-D (nmol/L) (Before)	Vit-D (nmol/L) (After 6months)
TKA	30	49.09±11.13	37.503±5.9456
TKA+anti	30	42.87±12.81	64.153±8.2698
KOA+anti	30	41.8±12.62	65.987±5.5764
F/H值		3.118	25.075
P值		0.049	0

Vitamin D is always linked to knee problems. The vitamin D level in the first group was 49.09 before TKA and reduced to 37.503 after 6 months. The preoperative vitamin D level of the second group of patients receiving TKA with anti-osteoporosis medicine was 42.87 nmol per liter. Six months later, the vitamin levels had risen to 64.153nmol per liter. The vitamin level increased from 41.8 to 65.987 nmol per liter in the third group receiving just anti-osteoporosis Knee osteoarthritis. Using ANOVA, the mean F/H value was 3.118 before surgery and 25.075 six months later. It was statistically significant ($P > 0.05$) to compare Vit-D levels before and after surgery.

Table 4: The table showing β -CTX before treatment and after 6 months of treatment

Group	N	β -CTX (pg/ml) (Before)	β -CTX (pg/ml) (After 6months)
TKA	30	503.68±204.37	633.72±240.95
TKA+anti	30	727.1±290.79	372.273±122.2867
KOA+Anti	30	726.4±302.56	318.173±89.3215
H值		11.493a	57.597
P值		0.003	0.01

All three groups' Bone remodeling biomarker, β -CTX, was analyzed. These biomarkers were studied before and after therapy for 6 months. The first group had complete knee arthroplasty, the β -CTX level was 503.68 picograms per milliliter, and six months later, β -CTX was 633.72. It reveals that bone strength Improved; the β -ctx level in the second group treated with total knee arthroplasty with anti-osteoporosis medicine was 727.1

picogram per milliliter. After 6 months of surgery, it was 372.273. In the third group, the amount of β -CTX dropped from 726.4 to 318.173 picogram per milliliter. The last two groups of β -CTX dropped during 6 months. The H test results were 11.493 before surgery and 57.597 after 6 months of treatment. The P test results were 0.003 before surgery and after 6 months of treatment. β -CTX levels before and after surgery were statistically significant ($P < 0.05$).

Table 5: The table showing VAS before treatment and after 6 months of treatment

Group	N	VAS (Before)	VAS (After 6 months)
TKA	30	5.82±1	2.16±0.51
TKA+anti	30	5.6±0.96	1.59±0.46
KOA+Anti	30	5.67±0.93	3.61±0.96
F/H值		0.402	56.136
P值		0.67	0.03

The visual analog scale was used to measure the success of the proposed treatments. The

The first group of patients had a VAS score of 5.821 before surgery and 2.160.51 after 6 months. The preoperative VAS score for the second group receiving total knee arthroplasty and anti-osteoporosis medicine was 5.60.96, while the postoperative VAS score was 1.590.46. The VAS score for the third group receiving only anti-osteoporosis medication decreased from 5.67.93 to 3.61.96. Postoperative VAS scores decreased in all groups, especially the second group. The ANOVA revealed that the mean F/H value and mean P-value were 0.402 and 0.67 before surgery and 56.136 and six months later. It was statistically significant ($P < 0.05$), 6 months after surgery. Preoperative VAS did not differ between the three groups ($P > 0.05$).

Discussion:

Osteoporosis and Osteoarthritis have had a significant impact on older adults's quality of life. There is a significant amount of literature indicating that osteoporosis (OP) is one of the causes of Osteoarthritis (OA) [5]. Furthermore, there is a strong correlation between the two, and older people with osteoporosis frequently have Osteoarthritis of the knee. The two diseases are more likely to coexist in the same person. The decrease in bone tissue caused by osteoporosis may further aggravate KOA [6]. Patients with Osteoarthritis of the knee combined with osteoporosis [7]. We point out that osteoporosis exacerbates the disease progression of Osteoarthritis of the knee. Therefore, for the treatment of patients with Osteoarthritis of the knee combined with osteoporosis, we should pay attention to the treatment of osteoporosis and not separate the two diseases. Many studies indicate that women over the age of 60 and men over the age of 70 have their bone mineral density (BMD) measured before undergoing surgery TKA to avoid poor outcomes [8]. Aside from that, poor

bone quality can have a detrimental impact on patient satisfaction with the surgical outcome of TKA. As a result, minimizing bone loss and extending the life of a prosthesis are critical considerations in total knee arthroplasty. A septic loosening and migration of components have all been reported in the setting of TKA [9–13]. BMD assessment before TKA has played a marginal role in the clinical setting. The loss of bone in osteoporosis patients has been shown to harm TKA, resulting in decreased stability, a shorter lifespan of the prosthesis, and a higher risk of revision [14, 15]. Initial implant micromotion and migration are two factors that contribute to periprosthetic bone loss. Osteoporosis is typically considered a risk factor for periprosthetic fracture during or after the procedure [16-19]. Recent research has also revealed that osteoporosis impacts tibial component position in primary TKA and survival following a periprosthetic fracture [17]. We believe that the treatment in patients with Osteoarthritis of the knee combined with osteoporosis, in addition to relieving joint pain and promoting functional recovery, strengthening joint stability and improving muscle strength of the patient's lower limbs are also the key to treatment [20-22]. In contrast, the treatment of osteoporosis can improve bone mass, strengthen body balance, improve muscle strength and further strengthen joint stability). The primary cause of Osteoarthritis is bodyweight, but it has been shown that weight change in women has a negative effect on the development of Osteoarthritis of the knee. The risk of knee osteoarthritis was greater in those with a higher body mass index (BMI). Changes in body size were directly associated with the risk of knee osteoarthritis. The main mechanism for that weight gain increases the joint load and mechanical wear and tear caused by joint movement. Suppose the increase in body weight increases the compressive stress on the lateral cartilage of the knee joint, and the lateral side of the joint is the site of Osteoarthritis of the knee. In that case, it is suggested that high body weight may also be a major risk factor for the development of severe knee osteoarthritis. [23] found that patients with osteoporosis (OP) were significantly more likely to develop knee osteoarthritis (KOA). In contrast, Estrogen level plays an important role in maintaining the balance of human bone metabolism. It has been suggested that the occurrence of Osteoarthritis of the knee is closely related to estrogen receptors [24]. Estrogen deficiency also plays an important role in the pathogenesis of osteoporosis, and the two show a positive correlation. It has been found that postmenopausal women are significantly more likely to suffer from osteoporosis and Osteoarthritis (OA). In patients who are about to undergo total knee arthroplasty (TKA), preoperative and postoperative anti-osteoporosis treatment can promote recovery and positively impact the prognosis of patients after surgery [25]. So early anti-osteoporosis treatment for such patients can prevent the further aggravation of Osteoarthritis of the knee and alleviate the clinical symptoms of Osteoarthritis of the knee and play a role in preventing the occurrence of Osteoarthritis.

Osteotriol triol (active vitamin D) improves muscle strength and body balance. After TKA, patients with KOA reported higher satisfaction with anti-osteoporosis medication [26]. Osteotriol is the active vitamin D (1,25-(OH)2D3), commonly deficient, especially in patients with osteoporosis; Vitamin D deficiency or lack of vitamin D is still a global problem. Studies have reported that the risk of Osteoarthritis of the knee is three

times higher in people with low serum vitamin D levels than in normal people [27]. Low-level vitamin D may directly affect articular cartilage and accelerates the progression of Osteoarthritis of the knee [28]. Experts recommend that postmenopausal women or those over 65 years of age need to take 800 U of vitamin D daily to reduce bone loss and prevent osteoporosis effectively. Our study showed a significant increase in vitamin D levels in two groups after 6 months of treatments. So we can assume that antiosteoporosis medicines play a significant role in enhancing vitamin D in the succeeding 6 months of treatment. Before surgery, the decreased vitamin D level causes different functional disturbances, but these improved after 3 months of surgery due to the supply of vitamin D.

Jintenge capsules are a Chinese traditional medicine (CTM) increasing bone density. The Effect of Jintenge capsules on bone density is related to the hardness and toughness of human bones by increasing bone density to its richness in its calcium content [29]. Studies have demonstrated that Jintenge capsules can alter the structure of bone trabeculae, enhancing alkaline phosphatase activity and decreasing tartrate-resistant acid phosphatase activity, therefore promoting bone formation and limiting bone resorption [30]. Moreover, the study found that the therapy group's pain alleviation was greater and lasted longer than only TKA, which relieved patients' pain faster and better.

Carbocalcitonin is a synthetic calcitonin derivative used to treat osteoporosis-related bone discomfort [31]. It is also helpful against osteoarthritis and osteoporosis pain, making it appropriate for people with knee osteoarthritis and osteoporosis. Calcitonin regulates osteoclast activity, slows bone resorption, prevents calcium loss, and lowers serum calcium in hypercalcemia. It can increase bone hardness, calcium concentration, density, and cortical thickness. Our clinical dosage is one injection every 3 days, and a course of treatment is 5 injections every 6 months. They return to the hospital a month later to assess their bone density and metabolic index. Therefore, the use of anti-osteoporotic drugs before and after surgery is particularly important in patients with KOA who have undergone TKA with Osteoarthritis of the knee would help to improve the function of the knee.

Conclusion:

In summary, postoperative with anti-osteoporosis drugs for KOA patients undergoing TKA can improve the therapeutic Effect, increase bone density, reduce postoperative pain, promote functional recovery of the knee joint and can, prevent worsening of the disease also reduce the rate of surgery in patients with Osteoarthritis of the knee combined with osteoporosis. Anti-osteoporosis treatment can control osteoporosis, one of the possible causes of Osteoarthritis of the knee, and achieve a good clinical effect on the clinical symptoms of Osteoarthritis of the knee. Comparing these three groups, in the first and second groups who took the anti-osteoporosis medicine, the B-CTX was reduced, vitaminD3 was increased, and n-mid and BMD were decreased. On the other hand, it can effectively prevent postoperative sinking and loosening of the prosthesis

or periprosthetic fracture (PF) caused by osteoporosis in knee replacement patients, which can significantly improve the prognosis.

Declarations:

Ethical Approved and Consent to participate: Approved by the Department of Traumatology, The Second Affiliated Hospital of Kunming Medical University, Kunming, Yunnan, China

Consent for publication: All authors have reviewed and confirmed the accuracy of the whole manuscript

Consent to participate: Obtained

Availability of data and materials: The data sets used and analyzed during the current study are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

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Author contributions:

Substantial contributions to conception and design: DH, ZHG,

Data collection, analysis and interpretation of results: DH, MAH

All authors Drafting the article or critically revising it for important intellectual content.

All author's approval of the version to be published. All authors have read and approved the manuscript.

References

- [1]. Sharp SC, Hellings JA. Efficacy and safety of selective serotonin re-uptake inhibitors in the depression in children and adolescents[J]. *Clin Drug Invest*, 2006, 26(5) : 247-255.
- [2]. Bernatz JT, Brooks AE, Squire MW, Illgen RI 2nd, Binkley NC, Anderson PA (2019) Osteoporosis is common and undertreated prior to total joint arthroplasty. *J Arthroplasty* 34(7):1347–1353
- [3]. Chang CB, Kim TK, Kang YG, Seong SC, Kang SB (2014) Prevalence of osteoporosis in female patients with advanced knee osteoarthritis undergoing total knee arthroplasty. *J Korean Med Sci* 29(10):1425–1431
- [4]. Lingard EA, Mitchell SY, Francis RM et al (2010) The prevalence of osteoporosis in patients with severe hip and knee osteoarthritis awaiting joint arthroplasty. *Age Ageing* 39(2):234–239

- [5]. Wu Kebao,Chai, Li yong, Medical clinical analysis of two hundred and sixteen cases of integrated prevention and treatment of knee osteoarthritis[J]. Journal of Hunan Normal University (Medicine Edition),2016,13(6):131-133.
- [6]. Duvuri D, Li Chen, Grgull B, et al. DNA to trigger autoimmunity Experimental evidence that somatic undergoing mutated-self I mutation the potential [J]. Physiotherapy theory and practice 2016, 75 (08) : 874 – 889.
- [7]. Adriaan Louw,Kory Zimney,Jordan Reed,et al.Immediate preoperative outcomes of pain neuroscience education for patients undergoing total knee arthroplasty: A case series[J].Physiotherapy theory and practice,2019,35(6):543-553.
- [8]. Berenbaum F, Wallace IJ, Lieberman DE, Felson DT (2018) Modern-day environmental factors in the pathogenesis of Osteoarthritis. *Nat Rev Rheumatol* 14:674–681
- [9]. Anderson PA, Morgan SL, Krueger D, Zapalowski C, Tanner B, Jeray KJ, Krohn KD, Lane JP, Yeap SS, Shuhart CR, Shepherd J (2019) Use of bone health evaluation in orthopedic surgery: 2019 ISCD ofcial position. *J Clin Densitom* 22:517–543
- [10]. Frenzel S, Vecsei V, Negrin L (2015) Periprosthetic femoral fractures—incidence, classification problems and the proposal of a modified classification scheme. *Int Orthop* 39:1909–1920
- [11]. Peerakul Y, Leeyaphan J, Rojjananukulpong K (2021) The association between bone mineral density and postoperative drainage volume following cruciate-substituting primary total knee arthroplasty: a cross-sectional study. *Knee Surg Relat Res* 33:22
- [12]. Hampton CB, Berliner ZP, Nguyen JT, Mendez L, Smith SS, Joseph AD, Padgett DE, Rodriguez JA (2020) Aseptic loosening at the tibia in total knee arthroplasty: a function of cement mantle quality? *J Arthroplast* 35:S190–S196.
- [13]. Purudappa PP, Ramanan SP, Tripathy SK, Varatharaj S, Mounasamy V, Sambandam SN (2020) Intra-operative fractures in primary total knee arthroplasty—a systematic review. *Knee Surg Relat Res* 32:40.
- [14]. Jain S, Camacho P. Use of bone turnover markers in the management of osteoporosis. *Curr Opin Endocrinol Diabetes Obes.* 2018;25(6):366–72
- [15]. Huang CC, Jiang CC, Hsieh CH, Tsai CJ, Chiang H. Local bone quality affects the outcome of prosthetic total knee arthroplasty. *J Orthop Res.* 2016;34(2): 240–8. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jor.23003>.
- [16]. Valladares RD, Nich C, Zwingenberger S, Li C, Swank KR, Gibon E, Rao AJ, Yao Z, Goodman SB. Toll-like receptors-2 and 4 are overexpressed in an experimental model of particle-induced osteolysis. *J Biomed Mater Res A.* 2014;102(9):3004–11. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jbm.a.34972>

- [17]. Johnston AT, Tsiridis E, Eyres KS, Toms AD (2012) Periprosthetic fractures in the distal femur following total knee replacement: a review and guide to management. *Knee* 19(3):156–162.
- [18]. Orfanos G, Lim J, Youssef B (2019) Evaluating risk factors following surgery for periprosthetic fractures around hip and knee arthroplasties. *Arch Orthop Trauma Surg* 139(4):475–482.
- [19]. Rhee SJ, Cho JY, Choi YY, Sawaguchi T, Suh JT (2018) Femoral periprosthetic fractures after total knee arthroplasty: new surgically oriented classification with a review of current treatments. *Knee Surg Relat Res* 30(4):284–292
- [20]. Zhang L, Choi HJ, Estrada K, et al. Multistage genome-wide association meta-analyses identified two new loci for bone mineral density *J Human molecular genetics*, 2019,34 (3) : 505 – 516.
- [21]. Chen L, Duvvuri B, Grigull J, et al. Experimental evidence that mutated-self peptides derived from mitochondrial DNA somatic mutations have the potential to trigger autoimmunity[J]. *Hum Immunol*, 2014, 75 (08) : 873 – 879.
- [22]. Adriaan Louw, Kory Zimney, Jordan Reed, et al. Immediate preoperative outcomes of pain neuroscience education for patients undergoing total knee arthroplasty: A case series[J]. *Physiotherapy theory and practice*, 2019, 35 (6) : 543 – 553
- [23]. Horikawa A Im At . The relationship between Bone and Mineral Metabolism, *Journal of Osteoarthritis and osteoporosis* 2020, 39 (10) : 1223 – 1226.
- [24]. Wlwekil PHD, Mohasseb D , Glkoffash D, et al . Egyptian Rheumatologist and osteoporosis in primary Serum leptin postmenopausal women with Knee osteoporosis., 2019, 34 (1) : 21 - 24.
- [25]. Wlwekil PHD, Mohasseb D , Glkoffash D, et al . Egyptian Rheumatologist and osteoporosis in primary Serum leptin postmenopausal women with Knee osteoporosis., 2019, 34 (1) : 21 - 24.
- [26]. Gechen , PH li ,Fisch CC , et al. A study of total knee arthroplasty outcome of prosthetic. *Journal of subchondral bone Bmc with Orthopaedic Musculoskeletal Research*, 2020,97(6):461-464.
- [27]. Wu N, Wang QP, Li H, et al. Relationships between serum iponectin, leptin concentrations and bone mineral density, and bone biochemical markers in chinese women[J]. *Clin Clim Acta*, 2010, 11(9 - 10) : 771-775.
- [28]. Zhang Z, Ye B, Zhang H L, et al. Effect of anti-osteoporosis treatment on the efficacy of age-related knee osteoarthritis[J]. *Practical Geriatrics*, 2011, 25(4):346-2.

[29]. Fang Z, Xia X, Li G, et al. Effect of salmon calcitonin on perioperative pain in elderly patients with osteoporosis undergoing total knee replacement[J]. Chinese Journal of Pain Medicine, 2011, 17 (11) : 650 - 653.

[30]. H Nakayama, S Yoshiya, U Stöckle, et al. Development of the double level osteotomy in severe varus osteoarthritis showed good outcome by preventing oblique joint line[J]. Archives of orthopaedic and trauma surgery, 2019, 139 (4) : 519 - 527.

[31]. Chris Allen, Riley Sheehan, Gail Deyle, et al. A manual physical therapy intervention for symptoms of knee osteoarthritis and associated fall risk: A case series of four patients[J]. Physiotherapy theory and practice, 2019, 35 (4) : 392 – 400.

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